

Chemical Examination of *Launea pinnatifida* Cass.

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Launea pinnatifida Cass is a small plant often found in abundance on the sandy coasts of India and is known to be useful as a substitute for *Taraxacum*¹. No report of the chemical examination of this plant has appeared in literature so far. We, now report, in this communication, the isolation of two triterpenes, teraxasterol from the leaves and teraxeryl acetate from the roots of the plant.

n-Hexane extracts of the leaves gave a colourless crystalline product (A), m.p. 221-222° .. (α)^{30°}_D +94.6° (CHCl₃), with a molecular formula, C₃₀H₅₀O. (A) gave positive colour reactions for triterpenes, formed an acetate, m.p. 251-252°, (α)^{30°}_D +101° (CHCl₃), (molecular formula, C₃₂H₅₂O₂), and a benzoate, m.p. 239-240°, (α)^{30°}_D +108° (CHCl₃) (molecular formula, C₃₇H₅₄O₂). (A) was identified as teraxasterol by a mixed melting point with an authentic sample of teraxasterol, its acetate and its benzoate.

The roots on extraction with n-hexane yielded colourless glistening crystals, (B), m.p. 303-304°, (α)^{30°}_D +8.5° (CHCl₃), with a molecular formula, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ which gave positive triterpene colour reactions. (B), on alkaline hydrolysis gave an alcohol, m.p. 282-283°, (α)^{30°}_D +0° (CHCl₃), (molecular formula, C₃₀H₅₀O) which formed a benzoate, m.p. 292-293°, (α)^{30°}_D +36° (CHCl₃), (molecular formula, C₃₇H₅₄O₂). (B) was identified as teraxeryl acetate by a mixed melting point with an authentic sample of teraxeryl acetate.

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